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Applicability of a modified backward extrusion process on commercially pure aluminium

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Abstract

In this study, a modified novel backward extrusion process implementing severe plastic deformation is presented for processing of ultrafine-grained materials. Deformation zone geometry was modified by elimination of mandrel's fillet for enhancing plastic strain and adding particular slope. Finite element analysis has been revealed higher strain value and more strain uniformity in this process. The process was applied to commercially pure aluminium, and microstructure and microhardness measurement were investigated. Surveying of microstructure in extruded specimen showed significant grain refinement resulted from the higher plastic strain of about 3.5 after only single pass new process. Uniform equivalent plastic strain through the thickness and length of the sample was achieved. Higher hydrostatic compression stress resulted from new die geometry limits the formation of any defects. Microhardness evolution in extruded part showed more than 52% improvement.

Keywords: New backward extrusion; FE Analysis; Grain refinement; Shear deformation.

1-Introduction

Backward extrusion is a conventional metal forming process which has been widely surveyed by lots of researchers [1-5]. This process is an appropriate method for manufacturing of close-ended products which have some advantages over the other production techniques [6]. Material consumption, higher dimensional accuracy and surface quality, adequate mechanical and microstructural properties and elimination of subsequent operations are some advantages of this method [7]. Backward extrusion has significant

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capabilities, although, there are some limitations. Unsteady deformation zone is one of problems which creates a different strain distribution through the extruded part. Therefore, inhomogeneous mechanical property and microstructure are predictable in the extruded products [3].

Severe plastic deformation processes are methods in which an intensive plastic strain is applied to the material to produce high strength ultrafine-grained (UFG) materials [8]. Compared with severe plastic deformation (SPD) processes, conventional metal forming processes such as extrusion, forging and rolling could not apply very high strains because the strain rate and lower hydrostatic stresses. Also, when applying higher amount of strains, increase of the area reduction are needed to lead to the work pieces with sorely thin and unprofitable. As a result, SPD processes have been admitted to the kind of metal forming processes with no change in final products shape [9]. In addition, some of the SPD processes cannot be used in industrial scale [10]. However, SPD processes are progressing by development of continuous processes like ECAP-conform [11], and Continuous HPT [12], but the need for industrial large samples and productive processes exists. Maybe, development of new combined processes with the capability of applying higher strains through single pass of conventional methods would be a good solution which have not received much attention yet.

New backward extrusion method is a process with new die design using enclosed billet and stable deformation zone. In this process, strain level increases and some disadvantages of conventional backward extrusion eliminates [13]. Fig. 1 illustrates the schematic of new backward extrusion process. In this process, the original billet has been enclosed in mandrel's hole and a punch strokes down to flow the material into a gap between the mandrel and die to form a cup-shaped sample. The limited deformation zone reduces requirement extrusion force, moreover obtaining higher strains in comparison with conventional backward extrusion were two advantageous of the method [13].

Producing lightweight products for different industries has found much attention recently. Aluminum and its alloys found various applications because of its lower density [14]. In addition, well formability of aluminum alloys makes them suitable for the extrusion processes. So, investigation of the applicability of new backward extrusion on aluminium and its alloys seems to be essential.

In this paper, the deformation zone geometry is improved for obtaining severe plastic strains and achieving uniform strain distribution compared to the new backward extrusion. The improved novel

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backward extrusion process is applied to a commercially pure Al, and the microstructure, mechanical properties and deformation behaviour are investigated.

Fig. 1. Schematic of new backward extrusion.

2- Principles of Modified novel backward extrusion

Fig. 1 demonstrates that the deformation in new backward extrusion starts when the billet flows to the first part of the deformation zone. A particular fillet has been provided in die geometry for reducing extrusion force and better material flow [13]. Though, this causes reduction in the extrusion force, the amount of strain is decreased. Therefore, this part of presented model modified with minimal corner radius for obtaining more shear strain as shown in Fig. 2. Also, higher hydrostatic backpressure is obtained which is necessary for SPD processing. Another improvement for creation of backpressure is a particular slope on the mandrel as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Schematic of modified novel backward extrusion.

3- Experimental and FE procedures

In this study, a commercially pure aluminum (99.8 %) has been used in the experimental tests. Table 1 illustrates the composition of the material used. Standard compression test according to [ASTM: E9-04](#) were conducted for obtaining stress-strain relationship at a strain rate of 10^{-4}s^{-1} at room temperature using a 30 tons Instron press. Fig. 3 illustrates the compression test setup and the sample before and after the test.

Table 1. Chemical composition of commercially pure Al.

Fig. 3. (a) compression test setup and (b) the test samples before and after the compression test.

Fig. 4. (a) Die setup and the components of modified new backward extrusion die (b) experimental test setup.

Initial cylindrical aluminum billets with 25 mm in diameter and 70 mm in length were machined from as-cast billet and is changed to a cup shaped product with 63 mm outer diameter and 3 mm wall thickness. A

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die was made from hot work steel H13 and hardened up to 55 HRC. Fig. 4 (a) illustrates the components of the modified new backward extrusion setup. Experimental tests have been done by 200-ton hydraulic press of Wykeham Farrance as shown in Fig. 4 (b). Die components including die, billet and mandrel are impregnated by graphite and grease for lubrication and then assembled. Extrusion process was done by pressing of punch down with speed of about 10 mm/min.

Microstructural investigations were conducted using optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The sample cross section were polished and then were etched by different chemical and electrochemical etching. Two different etchants of 4%HF+ 46%HCl+ 46%HNO₃+ 4%H₂O and 1%HF+ 33%HCl+ 33%HNO₃+ 33%CH₃OH were used for chemical etching. The first and second etchants were used for one and five seconds, respectively. Also, electrochemical etching has been utilized by using Barkers reagent (4ml HBF₄+0.5ml HCl+200ml H₂O) at the voltage of 30V at 0 °C temperature for 5 min holding time [15]. Increasing of holding time reveals grain boundaries which aligned in material flow direction. First etchant was used for this purpose with 1 min holding time. Vickers microhardness tests were done at 100 gr load for 15sec.

New backward extrusion has been simulated using DEFORMTM3D software. Adaptive remeshing and updated Lagrangian method are specific characteristic of DEFORM software for the metal forming process [16]. Material properties are main input data for the FE analysis. As mentioned, the stress-strain relationship extracted from the compression test and estimated by Hollomon's equation, $\sigma = K\varepsilon^n$, in which K and n were 111.14 MPa and 0.396, respectively. A constant shear friction with friction coefficient factor of 0.2 was considered in this simulation [17, 18]. All of the parts in finite element model except the billet have been considered as rigid parts. Because of symmetry, one-fourth of the billet were modeled. Totally 8075 number of tetrahedral type elements with linear shape function were used to mesh the billet.

4. Results and discussion

Fig. 5 illustrates the pictures of the cross section of the extruded specimen during the novel modified backward extrusion process and the initial billet. The initial cylindrical billet experiences two shear zones of 1 and 2 and a decreasing gap between them. Existence of two shear zones could increase the equivalent plastic strain by accumulation of higher shear strains to the normal strains resulted from the extrusion process. Decreasing gap will increase the hydrostatic compression stress, a necessary component for SPD

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processing, on the sample. After passing the material from the shear zone 2, higher plastic strain of the process may produce an ultrafine-grained microstructure.

Fig. 5 (a) the initial billet and (b) sample during the new process.

Fig. 6 Comparison between deformation behavior by (a) FEA gridding model (b) over etched extruded part divided to five regions by dashed yellow lines.

Fig. 6 (a) and (b) show a comparison between the cross section of the sample during the process resulted from the FE grid model and the experiment (etched sample). Grain boundaries coupled to the material flow has been revealed by the over etching process. As can be seen, both the gridd model and over etched sample showed two areas with higher shear strains. When the material passed from the first shear zone, grains are oriented on special directions. Also, the slope on mandrel prevents easy flow and increases the amount of hydrostatic stress. However, severe contact's effect is more and non-uniform strain through the thickness with various grid sizes have been recognized in Fig. 6 (a). Second shear zone causes to apply more shear strain on the sample and to achieve more grain refinement. Considering two shear zones, the cross section of the sample can be divided to five different areas as are shown in Fig. 6 (b).

To investigate the process of grain refinement in the novel backward extrusion process, the microstructures of different regions were investigated by optical microscopy. Fig. 7 illustrates the microstructure of five different zones of the sample which experiences different strain history. Homogenous equiaxed microstructure of the zone *I* which is a result of constrained compression strain state is seen in the Fig. 7 (a). Strain state of constrained compression has almost no effect on the microstructure [5, 19]. With the arrival of the material to the deformation zone, grains coupled to the material flow and started to be oriented as shown in Fig. 7(b). The microstructures of the material in the zone *II* (points *a* and *b*) were shown in Fig. 7 (b) and (c). These microstructures are related to the shear zone *I*, and show elongated grains along the $\sim 90^\circ$ rotated from extrusion direction (ED). This area and all the material passed, experience plastic strains of about 1.7. In the last researches, the effect of plastic strain on grain refinement, the plastic strain were divided to shear and normal strains which have a different effect on the grain refinement [20-22]. It has been reported that the shear strain has a principle role in grain refinement and the deformation areas with maximum shear strains has better condition for grain refinement [23-25]. As mentioned, in the modified

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new backward extrusion process, the amount of effective strain is very high which some part of it resulted from passing the material from two shear zones. The shear strain in point *a* is approximately zero, and there is no tangible change in the microstructure while higher shear strain of points *b* and *c* creates better grain refinement. The microstructure of point *d*, region *III*, shows elongated fine grains almost similar to region *II* as illustrates in Fig. 7 (d). This point experience both shear strains and normal strains resulted from decreasing gap of mandrel slope. The material passed from shear zone 2 experiences higher strain level ($\epsilon \sim 3$) and shows very refined severely elongated microstructure as shown in Fig. 7 (e). Excessive grain elongation and distribution of fine-grained structure in the point *f*, zone *V*, verifies high level of exposed strain in this region ($\epsilon \sim 4$).

Fig. 7 Microstructure of nine points of the sample which recognized on extruded part.

Fig. 8 shows the effective strain distribution of the sample in different stages of new backward extrusion process. The strain level is increased sharply after passing the material from the shear zones of *1* and *2*. Moreover, some parts of the sample remain undeformed with inhomogeneous mechanical and microstructural properties [21, 22]. In Fig. 8 (b), the effective strain varies through the thickness of the extruded part in which the strain increases from the upper contact surface to the bottom. Severe frictional contact between the bottom surface of the extruded part and die is the main reason of this difference. Moreover, mandrel's slope is another reason for this trend. Although, higher back pressure creates an uniform effective strain distribution. In Fig. 8 (c), uniform effective strain distribution along the longitudinal direction of the extruded tube is seen.

Fig. 8. The effective strain distributions in modified new backward extrusion in different stages.

Distribution of effective strain through the wall thickness varies as shown in Fig. 9. As is seen, the amount of effective strain increases from the inner to the outer surface of the extruded material. Fig. 9 shows a comparison between the strain distribution resulted from this work and previously presented work in reference [26]. This figure shows an uniform through thickness strain distribution with standard deviation (SD) of 0.6 compared to that in the previous work with SD of 0.8. Better strain distribution may be reflected the higher hydrostatic stress produced from the mandrel's slope. Also, average effective strain in this work (3.33) is higher than that (2.81) in the previous work [26]. Higher plastic strain with better homogeneity is a critical factor in SPD processing.

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Fig. 9 The effective strain distribution through the thickness of the specimen.

The effect of the slope of mandrel which increase the hydrostatic compression stresses could also be seen in SEM micrographs of the near surface microstructure in different critical zones as shown in Fig. 10. Obviously, there are no surface cracks and defects in the critical areas where are more talented for crack initiation. In other SPD processes like ECAP, crack propagation increases without back pressure with non-uniform strain distribution and localized strain in particular areas. Therefore back pressure has shown a significant effect on uniform strain distribution and prevention of defects [27, 28]. In the other word, the slope of the mandrel in modified new backward extrusion process has a role similar to the back pressure in ECAP process.

Fig. 10 SEM micrograph from three critical zones of the extruded part.

Amount of plastic strain affects to the grain refinement and mechanical properties in the metal forming processes [13]. In addition, the hardness and strength are related to the grain size based on hall-petch relationship [20]. Therefore, measurement of the hardness could be a useful criterion for investigation of strain distribution and mechanical properties of the deformed material. Microhardness and effective strain distributions in the extruded part along the particular paths of *AB*, *CD*, *EF* and *FG* (Fig. 11 (a)) are shown in Figs. 11(b)-11(e). Hardness distribution along *AB*, shown in Fig. 11 (b), shows an average hardness of about 40 Hv in undeformed area which has no considerable plastic strain. Hardness increases up to ~48 Hv along *CD* path at the bottom of the sample where the effective strain increases to about 0.5 (Fig. 11 (c)). Gradual increasing of the hardness and effective strain along *DF* is shown in Fig. 11 (d). The hardness enhanced to ~ 56Hv at the outer region of the extruded part where the material experiences the highest strain of 2.8 through *DF*. Finally, uniform hardness distribution and constant effective strain along *FG* (Fig. 14 (e)) shows uniform mechanical properties in the modified new backward extrusion along the longitudinal direction. Average hardness of about 63 Hv in the longitudinal direction of the processed sample via modified new backward extrusion was achieved. In the other word, the hardness increases more than 53 % at the strain of about 3. Comparison of the hardness of the sample with that in the other works done previously on the same material and plastic strain [10, 20, 29] shows a good agreements.

Fig. 11 Equivalent plastic strain contour and measurement paths (a) and Vickers microhardness and effective strain curves of extruded part through different path of *AB* (b) *CE* (c) *DF* (d) and *FG* (e).

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Fig. 12 Comparison of load-stroke curve resulted from FE and experiment.

The extrusion force versus displacement resulted from experimental test and FE was compared in Fig. 12. It can be seen that the experimental force is lower than FE force up to red dashed line, while after that the trend is reversed. This behavior may be attributed to the frictional state which is changed during the process. As mentioned, experimental test starts with lubrication of die parts and the billet. The friction coefficient at the start of the process is lower than that at the final stages because the lubricant may be scape during the test. This behavior is not considered in FE simulations, and constant friction condition was used. Comparison of the pick extrusion force resulted from FE and experiment which were 30 tons, and 33 tons respectively, showed a good agreement.

5- Conclusion

In this study, a modified novel backward extrusion process was applied to the commercially pure aluminium, and following conclusions could be made:

- Modified novel backward extrusion process was successfully applied to the pure aluminium and significant grain refinement was achieved.
- Higher plastic strain of ~ 3.5 were obtained which is very higher than conventional backward extrusion.
- Deformation zone geometry was modified to enhancing the amount of strain, prevention of probable defect and more strain uniformity.
- Hardness was increased to about 63 Hv from the initial value of ~40 Hv.
- Better strain homogeneity through the thickness and length of the sample were achieved.
- Higher hydrostatic stress was applied which make the process more effective for producing defect free samples.
- Higher hydrostatic stress maybe make the process suitable for processing brittle materials.

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Figures

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Fig. 7. Microstructure of nine points of the sample which recognized on extruded part.

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Fig. 10. SEM micrograph from three critical zones of the extruded part.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

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Fig. 12. Comparison of load-stroke curve resulted from FE and experiment.

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Table

Table 1. Chemical composition of commercially pure Al

Element	Al	Si	Fe	Ti	Cu	P	Ni
Value (% wt.)	Base	0.0365	0.0699	0.004	0.0143	0.0028	0.0041

Figure captions

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